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Abstract
<p>This report presents a reproducible framework for designing, manufacturing, and validating realistic biotissue phantoms that represent several tissue types and polarization-dependent optical phenomena. The developed phantoms incorporate confirmed and tunable optical properties, including scattering and depolarization, absorption, birefringence, and chirality, enabling controlled isolation of individual mechanisms that define measured signals in multidimensional imaging.</p> <p>The framework supports systematic characterization of imaging systems and provides well-defined test objects for assessing sensitivity to subsurface inhomogeneities, depth, geometry, surface roughness, and absorption-induced spectral modulation. Overall, these phantoms serve as repeatable reference standards for benchmarking instrumentation, validating analysis methods, and improving interpretation of complex biotissue imaging results.</p>

Public introduction¹
<p>This report describes a practical, repeatable method for creating tissue phantoms - artificial samples that mimic the appearance and behavior of real biological tissue when imaged with light. These phantoms can be tailored to imitate different tissue types and key optical effects, such as how tissue scatters and absorbs light, how fibrous structures change polarization, etc. By building these properties into well-controlled test samples, we can study each effect separately and understand how each influences what an imaging system measures. The framework also provides reliable test objects for checking how well imaging methods detect features below the surface and how results depend on depth, shape, surface roughness, and wavelength. Overall, these phantoms serve as consistent reference standards for evaluating imaging devices, validating data analysis approaches, and improving the interpretation of complex tissue images.</p>

¹ According to Deliverables list in Annex I, all restricted (RE) deliverables will contain an introduction that will be made public through the project WEBSITE

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1 INTRODUCTION

Biotissue phantoms are artificial, well-controlled samples designed to reproduce key optical properties of biological tissues. They provide a practical platform for isolating individual light-tissue interaction mechanisms and for evaluating how specific parameters influence measured signals and reconstructed images. In contrast to *in vivo* or *ex vivo* specimens, where multiple effects are coupled and biological variability is high, phantoms enable repeatable experiments, systematic parameter sweeps, validation of models, and benchmarking of imaging methods.

This project focuses on investigating multidimensional aspects of biotissue imaging using complex vector light across spatial, spectral, and polarization domains. Such multidomain measurements can provide richer contrast than intensity-only imaging, but they also require careful interpretation because polarization and coherence-related observables are influenced by multiple concurrent processes, including scattering, absorption, anisotropy, and structural organization.

To support these studies, we developed and tested a framework for manufacturing repeatable, complex biotissue phantoms that emphasize major polarization-related phenomena in light-tissue interaction. In particular, the phantoms were designed to reproduce (1) spatially varying and depth-dependent depolarization, (2) birefringence associated with organized fibrous structures, and (3) optical activity (chirality). This combination enables controlled investigation of how each effect manifests in polarization-resolved measurements and how the effects may coexist or confound one another in realistic samples.

Among these mechanisms, depolarization is often the dominant effect governing the propagation of polarized light in biological tissue due to multiple scattering. Birefringence can additionally be significant in tissues with aligned microstructure such as collagen-rich or fibrotic regions, where phase retardation accumulates along preferred axes. Depolarization is influenced by factors such as scatterer size and concentration, refractive index mismatch, tissue thickness, wavelength, and the degree of structural heterogeneity. Therefore, phantoms with tunable and well-characterized depolarization and anisotropy are essential for interpreting polarization contrast and for validating algorithms intended to retrieve meaningful tissue parameters.

1.1 Objective and scope of the deliverable as defined in the DoA

This deliverable addresses **WP3: 2D/3D tissue imaging with structured light**, and specifically supports Task 3.1, which focuses on the development and testing of realistic biotissue phantoms mimicking healthy and pathological tissues with well-defined opto-mechanical and structural properties. The objective of this deliverable is to present the design, fabrication, and initial characterization of realistic tissue phantoms representing different tissue types and pathological conditions. These phantoms exhibit controlled and quantifiable optical properties relevant to OPTIPATH's imaging approach, including scattering behaviour, chirality, linear dichroism, and birefringence. The developed phantoms provide a reproducible and well-characterised test platform for the calibration, validation, and benchmarking of the OPTIPATH structured-light imaging system and associated data analysis pipelines, and form a foundational input for subsequent tasks involving experimental imaging, system optimization, and AI-based tissue characterization.

2 SYSTEM FOR THE CHARACTERIZATION OF THE PHANTOMS

Phantom characterization was performed using a polarized hyperspectral imaging (HSI) system developed on the basis of a snapshot hyperspectral camera. A compact imaging setup (Fig. 1) was assembled using a hyperspectral snapshot camera equipped with a micro-Fabry-Perot tunable filter, providing a spectral resolution of 6–10 nm over the 510–900 nm wavelength range. Broadband illumination was provided by a halogen light source coupled to a fiber-optic ring illuminator (Edmund Optics, USA), which produced a near-uniform irradiance distribution within the camera field of view. The ring-illumination geometry enables coaxial illumination and detection. Both the illumination module and the camera were equipped with linear broadband polarizers, allowing acquisition in co-polarized and cross-polarized configurations.

Fig. 1. Schematic of the polarized HSI system: (1) lens hood (spacer), (2) fiber ring illuminator, (3) ring-shaped illumination polarizer, (4) camera polarizer, (5) built-in diffuse reflectance standard (gray Spectralon, 50% reflectance), (6) hyperspectral camera (510–900 nm; 6–10 nm spectral resolution).

The system acquires hyperspectral data cubes of reflected intensity in co-polarized (I_{\parallel}) and cross-polarized (I_{\perp}) modes. These measurements enable computation of the degree of linear polarization (DOLP) according to [1]:

$$DOLP(\lambda) = \frac{I_{\parallel}(\lambda) - I_{\perp}(\lambda)}{I_{\parallel}(\lambda) + I_{\perp}(\lambda)} \quad (1)$$

3 PHANTOMS WITH STRUCTURAL INHOMOGENEITIES MIMICKING TISSUE DEPOLARIZATION

3.1 Phantoms with the inclined layer of increased thickness

This phantom type (see Fig. 2) is designed to mimic histological tissue blocks containing localized regions of increased scattering. The phantoms were 3D printed using a stereolithographic approach from the polymer resins with a scattering modulated by the addition of ZnO nanopowder. The phantom includes an inclined scattering layer (the “inclusion”), whose thickness can be controlled from a few micrometers up to 3 mm. Owing to its regular, well-defined geometry, the inclusion provides a convenient means to systematically vary the fraction of strongly scattering material within the effective sampling volume of the measurement system. As the inclusion occupies an increasing portion of the sampling volume, multiple scattering becomes more pronounced, leading to enhanced depolarization of the reflected light. Consequently, the measured degree of linear polarization (DOLP) decreases with increasing inclusion volume within the system’s sampling depth (see Fig. 2d).

Fig.2. (a) - Schematics of the phantom. (b) - Layout of the measurement data. (c) - Image of the phantom: red and black arrows represent the beginning and the end of the inclined layer, respectively. The dashed line indicates the measurement position for the results shown in Fig. 3. (d) - DOLP spectra at the beginning and at the end of the inclined layer of increased thickness.

Fig.3. DOLP map measured across the phantom (along dashed line in Fig 2c.). Color vertical lines indicated the selected wavelength for a comparative analysis. (b) - DOLP profiles along the phantom for the selected wavelengths.

As the wavelength increases, the DOLP increases because scattering decreases at longer wavelengths (Fig. 2d). Since the inclusion does not contain a distinct chromophore, its baseline DOLP spectrum is a smooth, featureless curve. To introduce absorption contrast, a controlled amount of a red absorber was added to the inclusion (Fig. 4). In general, absorption tends to increase DOLP because it preferentially attenuates photons with long path lengths, thereby reducing the contribution of multiply scattered (and thus depolarized) light. In our case, this modification increased DOLP in the green spectral region. As a result, the measured DOLP spectra qualitatively and quantitatively resemble those observed in real biological tissues. An example of skin DOLP spectra is provided in [1].

Fig.4. (a) - Image of the phantom with modified absorption: red and black arrows represent the beginning and the end of the inclined layer, respectively. The dashed line indicates the measurement position presented in Fig.5. (b) - DOLP spectra at the beginning and at the end of the inclined layer of increased thickness.

Fig.5. (a) - DOLP map measured across the phantom (along dashed line in Fig 4a). Color vertical lines indicated the selected wavelength for a comparative analysis. (b) - DOLP profiles along the phantom for the selected wavelengths.

3.2 Phantoms with two inclined layers of increased thickness

A similar approach was used to fabricate a phantom containing two inclined inclusions with maximum depths of 2 mm and 3 mm, respectively (Fig. 6). This phantom was designed to evaluate whether the imaging system can distinguish between these two cases, which appear visually indistinguishable.

Fig.6. (a) - Schematics of the phantom with two inclined inclusions. (b) - Image of the phantom: red and black arrows represent the beginning and the end of the inclined layer, respectively. The dashed line indicates the measurement position for the results shown in Fig. 7. (c) and (d) - DOLP spectra at the beginning and at the end of the inclined layer of shallow inclusion (max 2 mm) and deeper inclusion (max 3 mm) correspondingly.

Fig.7. (a) - DOLP map measured across the phantom (along dashed line in Fig 6a). Color vertical lines indicated the selected wavelength for a comparative analysis. (b) - DOLP profiles along the phantom for the selected wavelengths.

Fig.8. (a) - Image of the phantom with two inclined inclusion and modified absorption: red and black arrows represent the beginning and the end of the inclined layers, respectively. The dashed line indicates the measurement position for the results shown in Fig. 9. (b) and (c) - DOLP spectra at the beginning and at the end of the inclined layer of deeper inclusion (max 3 mm) and shallow inclusion (max 2 mm) correspondingly.

Fig.9. (a) - DOLP map measured across the phantom (along dashed line in Fig 8a). Color vertical lines indicated the selected wavelength for a comparative analysis. (b) - DOLP profiles along the phantom for the selected wavelengths.

The differences between the inclusions are evident in the minimum DOLP values corresponding to them (Fig. 7b). In the absence of chromophores, this difference is observed across the entire wavelength range considered. When a chromophore is added (Fig. 9b), the separation between the minimum DOLP values associated with the deeper and shallower inclusions becomes smaller and is most pronounced at longer wavelengths.

3.3 Phantoms with a thin inclined cylinder

An additional test sample was fabricated to evaluate the system’s ability to visualize embedded objects. The sample consisted of a thin, inclined cylindrical inclusion with a nominal diameter of 0.6 mm (Fig. 10a). The cylinder was filled with the same inclusion material, doped with a red absorbing chromophore. The characterization results are presented in Figs. 10 and 11.

Fig.10. (a) - Schematics of the phantom containing an inclusion representing a thin inclined cylinder. (b) - Image of the phantom: red and black arrows represent the beginning and the end of the cylindrical inclusion, respectively. The dashed black line indicates the measurement direction along the cylinder, the dashed orange line – the position outside the inclusion for the results shown in Fig. 11. (c) - DOLP spectra at the beginning and at the end of the cylindrical inclusion.

Fig.11. (a) - DOLP map measured along the cylindrical inclusion (along the black dashed line in Fig 10a). Color vertical lines indicated the selected wavelength for a comparative analysis. (b) - DOLP profiles along the phantom for the selected wavelengths. Data shown with orange color indicates measurements outside the inclusion (along the orange dashed line in Fig 10a).

With the selected characterization method, the inhomogeneity is identified by comparing the signal measured along the inhomogeneity with that of the surrounding background (Fig. 11). This contrast becomes more pronounced at longer wavelengths, consistent with reduced scattering and increased effective penetration depth.

3.4 Phantoms with controllable roughness

Surface roughness is one of the factors influencing the measured DOLP in reflectance geometry. Microrelief on the sample surface alters the local angle of incidence and generates additional Fresnel reflections, refraction, and surface scattering. These effects can modify the polarization state of detected light independently of the bulk optical properties. Consequently, surface variations may cause systematic bias and increase variability in DOLP measurements, complicating sample comparisons and limiting the robustness of quantitative interpretation.

In many practical experiments, surface roughness is neither controlled nor systematically reported. A common approach to reduce surface effects is to apply an index-matching or immersion liquid to reduce the refractive-index mismatch at the interface and suppress surface scattering. However, this approach is not always feasible due to sample handling limitations, contamination risks, absorption of the liquid into porous materials, or limitations on *in vivo* measurements. As a result, surface effects can reduce measurement repeatability and introduce ambiguity in attributing DOLP changes to bulk tissue properties rather than to the interface.

Fig. 12. (a) – Example of surface roughness measurement by the optical profilometer for the samples processed with P180 sandpaper. (b) – Effect of surface roughness on the measured DOLP values of the light reflected from the phantom.

The proposed phantom concept enables systematic investigation of how surface roughness affects the considered measurement methods. To this end, the surfaces of the manufactured phantoms were mechanically processed using sandpapers with different grit sizes, ranging from coarse P180 to fine P1000. The resulting surface roughness was quantified using an optical profilometer, and a representative surface topography map for P180 case is shown in Fig. 12a.

The samples were subsequently characterized using the polarized HSI system, and the corresponding DOLP values were computed. The results are presented in Fig. 12b. The measurements indicate that surface roughness can noticeably influence the derived DOLP, with variations reaching up to ~10% across the tested roughness range.

3.5 Realistically shaped phantom mimicking a cancerous sample

To validate the imaging capabilities of the system under realistic conditions, we fabricated a phantom containing an inclusion with anatomically relevant geometry. The sample mimics a histological tissue block corresponding to a ductal carcinoma in situ (DCIS) specimen [2]. The 3D model used for printing (Fig. 13a) was generated from a histological image obtained and annotated by a pathology expert.

Fig.13. (a) – 3D phantom model. (b) - Image of the fabricated phantom.

Fig.14. DOLP maps of the phantom measured at (a): 600 nm, (b): 700 nm, (c): 800 nm, (d): 900 nm. (e) – Typical DOLP spectra for adipose and cancerous inclusion. The corresponding measurement areas are shown with rectangles of black and red colors.

The phantom represents two tissue types: adipose tissue and a cancerous inclusion. The scattering properties of the corresponding materials were tuned to represent these tissue types from a depolarization perspective. Our preliminary study indicates that cancerous regions exhibit stronger depolarization [2, 3], which can be clearly observed by using polarization-sensitive techniques, in contrast to methods based solely on scalar intensity. The results of polarized HSI characterization of the phantom are shown in Fig. 14 for several selected wavelengths. Representative DOLP spectra for the considered tissue types are presented in Fig. 14e.

Overall, realistic samples involve a complex interplay between tissue geometry, feature size, depth, and spatial variations in optical properties within the measurement volume. These coupled effects can be difficult to interpret without prior knowledge of signal behavior obtained from well-controlled tissue phantoms.

4 PHANTOMS WITH BIREFRINGENCE

A birefringence phantom was fabricated by incorporating a defined quantity of polypropylene fibers (27 μm in diameter). The fibers were aligned unidirectionally to form a flat bundle approximately 1 cm wide, which was placed inside a molding form. The phantom was then cast using a silicone-based fabrication protocol following the method described in [4]. Photographs of the resulting transparent and scattering phantoms are shown in Fig. 15.

Fig. 15. Image of the phantoms with birefringent inclusion in transparent (a) and scattering (b) matrix. The red vertical bar indicates the area selected for OCT inspection.

The manufactured phantom layer has been characterized with the OCT technique. The results are presented in Fig. 16. The images show the lateral and depth distribution of the fibers.

Fig. 16. OCT images of the birefringent layer of the phantom: (a) - B-scan across the layer showing the distribution of fibers; (b) – 3D image of the fiber layer. Scan area size: 2x4x1.8 mm

Further characterization has been performed with a polarized hyperspectral imaging camera. For the observation of the birefringence effect, the cross-fraction value $C(\varphi)$ defined according to the formula (2) has been computed.

$$C(\varphi) = \frac{I_{\perp}}{I_0} = \frac{I_{\perp}}{I_{\perp} + I_{\parallel}}, \quad (2)$$

where I_{\perp} is the reflected intensity measured at the crossed polarizers of the light source and detector. I_0 is the total reflected intensity, φ is the angle between the direction of the illuminating light polarization and the direction of the orientation of the fibers. For the weak absorption of the sample $I_0 \cong I_{\perp} + I_{\parallel}$. I_{\parallel} is the reflected intensity measured at a parallel orientation of the polarizers of the light source and detector. Cross-fraction depends on the orientation of the sample relative to the polarization of the illuminating radiation:

$$C(\varphi) \sim \sin^2(2\varphi)\sin^2\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right) \quad (3)$$

with a retardance δ defined as:

$$\delta(\lambda) = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \Delta n(\lambda) d, \tag{4}$$

where d is the path length through the birefringent region; $\Delta n(\lambda)$ is the birefringence of a material: the difference between two refractive indices seen by light polarized along two orthogonal principal axes. For a (linear) birefringent material $\Delta n = n_{slow} - n_{fast}$.

According to Eq. (3), the cross-fraction reaches its maximum at an orientation of 45° , and its minimum at 0° or 90° . In regions without birefringence, the cross-fraction C should be independent of the sample orientation relative to the incident polarization.

Figure 17 shows cross-fraction images acquired at different sample orientations. The oscillatory change in the cross-fraction (see Fig. 18) within the region expected to be birefringent confirms the presence of birefringence.

Fig. 17. Cross fraction images of the transparent phantom with a birefringent layer obtained at 600 nm at different rotation angles: (a) – 0° , (b) – 45° , (c) – 90° .

Fig. 18. Cross fraction values of a transparent phantom at different sample rotation angles. The oscillating signal corresponds to a birefringent area; the linear signal corresponds to an area without birefringence.

Similar characterization was performed for the birefringent area embedded into the scattering phantom. The results are presented in Fig. 19. However, in this case, the amplitude of the oscillating signal is 1.7 times lower due to the masking birefringence effect with the surrounding scattering.

Fig. 19. Cross fraction images of the scattering phantom with a birefringent layer obtained at 600 nm at different rotation angles: (a) – 0°, (b) – 45°, (c) – 90°, (d) – 135°, (e) – 180°. (f) – Cross fraction values of a scattering phantom at different sample rotation angles. The oscillating signal corresponds to a birefringent area, the linear signal corresponds to an area without birefringence.

5 CHIRALITY SENSING IN BIOTISSUE PHANTOMS

We developed a modular optical tissue phantom with independently controllable scattering properties and glucose concentration, explicitly designed to enable investigation of chirality-dependent phase effects using glucose as a relevant biologically important example. The phantom consists of a detachable scattering layer coupled to a transparent glass cuvette filled with aqueous glucose solutions of defined concentration and chirality. A series of scattering layers emulating optical properties ranging from nearly transparent to highly scattering biological tissues were fabricated following the protocol described in [5]. The layers were characterized by $z/l^* = 0, 2, 4, 6.5$ and 9.6 . Each scattering layer was affixed to the front surface of a standard optical glass cuvette (total thickness 6 mm, with 1 mm wall thickness on each side), which was subsequently filled with the glucose solution. This configuration enables controlled modulation of photon multiple-scattering effects independently from the glucose concentration and chirality. A schematic representation of the phantom architecture is shown in Fig. 20.

Fig. 20. Visualization of phantom structure.

Aqueous glucose solutions with concentrations of 50, 70, 90, 110, 130, and 150 mg/dL were prepared to span the physiological and clinically relevant glycemic range. To explicitly investigate chirality-dependent optical phase responses, two independent solution sets were prepared using D(+) glucose and L(−) glucose powders. This approach enables direct comparison of enantiomer-specific optical responses under identical scattering conditions.

Phantom characterization was performed using a modified Mach–Zehnder interferometer configured for orbital angular momentum (OAM) phase measurements, as described in [6]. In the sample arm, a phase-only spatial light modulator (SLM) was used to generate Laguerre–Gaussian (LG) beams with defined topological charge and polarization. The structured beam propagated through the phantom and was interfered with a planar reference wave. Phase information associated with the OAM mode was extracted using a Fourier-transform–based phase retrieval algorithm applied to the recorded interference patterns. This configuration enables high-sensitivity detection of phase perturbations induced by glucose concentration, multiple scattering, and molecular chirality. For each phantom configuration, ten consecutive frames were acquired at a stabilized ambient temperature of $21 \pm 0.5^\circ\text{C}$ and averaged to improve the signal-to-noise ratio. LG modes with topological charges $\ell = \pm 3$ were used throughout the experiments.

Figure 21 presents the relative OAM phase shifts as a function of glucose concentration for $\ell = +3$ and $\ell = -3$ modes, measured for both D(+) and L(−) glucose solutions in combination with selected scattering layers. The results demonstrate that the proposed method retains sensitivity to glucose-induced phase changes under transparent ($z/l^* = 0$), weakly scattering ($z/l^* = 2$), and highly scattering ($z/l^* = 9.6$) conditions, confirming the robustness of the approach against multiple scattering.

Importantly, the system exhibits clear sensitivity to glucose chirality. Specifically, $\ell = -3$ mode shows reduced sensitivity for D(+)-glucose, whereas the $\ell = +3$ mode exhibits reduced sensitivity for L(-)-glucose. This asymmetric OAM–chirality interaction provides direct evidence that structured-light phase sensing can discriminate molecular enantiomers even in optically turbid environments, highlighting the potential of the proposed phantom and measurement approach for chiral-selective biomedical sensing.

Fig. 21. Relative phase shift depending on the glucose concentration under transparent ($z/l^* = 0$), weakly scattering ($z/l^* = 2$), and highly scattering ($z/l^* = 9.6$) conditions in case of D(+) glucose and LG beam with $\ell = +3$ (a); in case of D(+) glucose and LG beam with $\ell = -3$ (b); conditions in case of L(-) glucose and LG beam with $\ell = +3$ (c); in case of L(-) glucose and LG beam with $\ell = -3$ (d).

6 CONCLUSION

In this deliverable, we established a reproducible framework for fabricating and validating realistic biotissue phantoms that capture key polarization-dependent light–tissue interaction mechanisms relevant for multidimensional (7D) digital pathology. Using a polarized hyperspectral imaging system as the primary characterization platform, we demonstrated phantoms with controlled structural inhomogeneities (inclined layers of variable thickness, dual-depth inclusions, and a thin cylindrical inclusion) that enable systematic probing of how feature size and depth within the sampling volume affect depolarization and DOP across wavelength, including the impact of added absorption.

We additionally quantified the influence of surface roughness, showing that surface scattering alone can introduce measurable DOLP variability, highlighting an often undercontrolled factor in practical reflectance measurements. Beyond depolarization, we implemented dedicated phantoms for birefringence (fiber-aligned layers) and chirality (glucose solutions combined with adjustable scattering layers), confirming detectable orientation-dependent polarization signatures and robust, enantiomer-sensitive phase responses even under increased turbidity.

This phantom platform provides a controlled, repeatable basis for benchmarking imaging hardware that will be developed further in the project, validating signal-interpretation models, and developing analysis algorithms for realistic samples in which geometry, depth, and optical-property heterogeneity are tightly coupled.

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